

**THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE
COMMUNICATION SKILLS GLOBALLY**

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Annotation: The pace of technological advancement has significantly accelerated in recent years. The introduction of modern technology has significantly transformed people's capacity to engage and communicate. It is now one of the most significant aspects that influences the acquisition of the English language. Due to its widespread recognition for cross-cultural and cross-linguistic communication, most online communication platforms utilize the English language. Social media has emerged as the most effective platform for individuals to communicate and connect with each other, outperforming other strong technologies built for fostering interpersonal interactions. Individuals derive advantages from utilizing it as it serves as a valuable means to enhance their proficiency in the English language. That is why a significant number of individuals opt to utilize popular social media platforms such as YouTube and Instagram.

Key words: Modern technology, communication, speaking skills, social media, connect, platforms.

Аннотация: В последние годы темпы технического прогресса значительно ускорились. Внедрение современных технологий существенно изменило способность людей взаимодействовать и общаться. Сейчас это один из наиболее важных аспектов, влияющих на овладение английским языком. Благодаря широкому признанию межкультурного и межъязыкового общения большинство

платформ онлайн-коммуникации используют английский язык. Социальные сети стали наиболее эффективной платформой для общения и общения людей друг с другом, превосходя другие мощные технологии, созданные для содействия межличностному взаимодействию. Люди получают преимущества от его использования, поскольку он служит ценным средством повышения уровня владения английским языком. Вот почему значительное количество людей предпочитают использовать популярные социальные сети, такие как YouTube и Instagram.

Ключевые слова: Современные технологии, общение, разговорные навыки, социальные сети, connect, платформы.

ANMERKUNG: Das Tempo des technologischen Fortschritts hat sich in den letzten Jahren deutlich beschleunigt. Die Einführung moderner Technologie hat die Fähigkeit der Menschen, sich zu engagieren und zu kommunizieren, erheblich verändert. Dies ist heute einer der wichtigsten Aspekte, die den Erwerb der englischen Sprache beeinflussen. Aufgrund ihrer weit verbreiteten Anerkennung für interkulturelle und intersprachliche Kommunikation verwenden die meisten Online-Kommunikationsplattformen die englische Sprache. Soziale Medien haben sich als die effektivste Plattform für Einzelpersonen herausgestellt, um miteinander zu kommunizieren und sich zu vernetzen, und übertreffen andere leistungsstarke Technologien, die zur Förderung zwischenmenschlicher Interaktionen entwickelt wurden. Einzelpersonen ziehen Vorteile aus der Nutzung, da sie als wertvolles Mittel dienen, um ihre Englischkenntnisse zu verbessern. Aus diesem Grund entscheiden sich viele Menschen dafür, beliebte soziale Medienplattformen wie YouTube und Instagram zu nutzen.

Schlüsselwörter: Moderne Technologie, Kommunikation, Sprechfähigkeiten, soziale Medien, Verbindung, Plattformen.

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, social media has had a significant impact on our ability to communicate in languages other than our own, particularly the global language, English. It's no secret that the use of social networks makes difficult tasks of mankind easier. This paper aims to assess the impact of social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and TikTok on language use, learning and proficiency. It examines the advantages and disadvantages of social media in relation to English language proficiency.[1] The introduction lays the groundwork by highlighting the widespread use of social media and its importance in the daily lives of many English language learners and speakers around the world. Thanks to this social network, the number of English learners is increasing day by day. Social media has both advantages and disadvantages due to the two-sided nature of the coin it represents. Written interactions allow us to express our thoughts, thus developing writing and reading skills. It also serves as a great platform for improving English speaking skills as users can exchange audio and video messages. However, social media sites may hinder the development of academic language skills because they do not adhere to strict rules governing English language conventions. At the same time, it is causing new slangs and terms to appear.

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Modern culture is increasingly becoming a prevalent means of communication through social networks, while also providing users with the opportunity to enhance their English skills. Social media offers users a wide range of items that aid in language learning and enable quick connection with native English speakers. Individuals can utilize the English language to engage in discussions, consume various forms of media, and remain informed about influential figures, all of which contribute to enhancing their vocabulary and comprehension abilities. Podcasts and other digital platforms offer instructional information aimed at enhancing the language proficiency of non-native speakers. English is extensively utilized by numerous individuals in both social

media platforms and daily interactions.[2] Given that social media platforms are predominantly developed in the English language, they can serve as a valuable resource for enhancing one's proficiency in English. Enhancing a diverse set of communication and interpersonal abilities. The strategies outlined in this portion of the book can now be found.

The coin has got two sides that are why you can read positive and negative effect social media to our communication and speaking skills in English language.

Positive Impacts

Encounter with a Variety of Linguistic Styles - Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram, among other social media sites, expose users to a diverse range of linguistic styles and dialects. This exposure improves linguistic comprehension and flexibility, promoting an awareness of many English dialects, such as American, British, and Australian English. Users come to informal idioms, vernacular, and idiomatic terms that enhance their vocabulary and cultural understanding. So that, you can improve your writing and comprehension skills on these social media.

Enhanced practice and increased engagement - Social media offers a platform for those who are not native English speakers to engage in language practice and enhance their linguistic abilities. Platforms such as Reddit, Quora, and LinkedIn provide places where users may participate in debates, solicit feedback, and enhance their written communication skills. The continuous engagement in English facilitates the rapid acquisition and mastery of the language.

Advancements in Linguistic Utilization - The character limitations imposed by networks such as Twitter incentivize users to employ brevity and ingenuity in their language usage. This limitation promotes creativity, resulting in the development of novel terms, abbreviations, and linguistic abbreviations that become integrated into the ever-changing digital vocabulary. For example, acronyms like "LOL" (laugh out loud) and "BRB" (be right back) have gained widespread recognition and usage.

Social media platforms provide language learners the opportunity to engage with English-speaking communities, promoting intercultural relationships and boosting

language acquisition. The user's text is enclosed in tags. By utilizing Facebook language exchange groups or language learning tools like Tandem and HelloTalk, language learners may interact with native speakers, leading to mutual progress in their respective languages.[3] Furthermore, these encounters promote global consciousness and enhance understanding of different cultures, in addition to developing language skills. Participating in social networking sites allows students to improve their vocabulary and improve their English writing skills. User-supplied text is contained within tags. This is an important element in the language learning process, as it increases students' self-confidence and reduces the level of anxiety in learning a new language.

Social media platforms allow users to express their views and ideas through messages, announcements, and comments, thus encouraging communication and encouraging creative writing. Applying character limits on social media networks like Twitter forces users to express themselves using short language, thus improving their writing skills. User input "One can create long articles and participate in blogging on sites like Medium to improve writing skills and provide more in-depth content".[4]

Negative Impacts

Adverse Effects- Decline in Formal Writing Proficiency - The informal nature of social media communication often leads to a decline in formal writing skills. The extensive utilization of shorthand, emoticons, and informal language has the potential to permeate professional and academic writing, therefore undermining the standards of traditional written English.[5] Over time, this deterioration might result in a reduced ability to create cohesive and grammatically correct written writings.

A surge in grammatical and spelling errors- There is an excessive number of grammatical errors and spelling issues on social media that are difficult to correct. Continual exposure to these mistakes might develop into a habit, particularly for young users or individuals who are still acquiring the language. The normalization process poses a danger to the integrity of language training as it has the potential to foster widespread acceptance of improper language usage.[6]

CONCLUSION

Social media offers both prospects and difficulties in enhancing English-language communication proficiency. While it offers essential experience, exposure, and creative opportunities, it also encourages the use of informal language and may contribute to deterioration in formal writing proficiency. Evaluating the advantages and disadvantages is essential for both educators and learners. By carefully evaluating the pros and downsides of social media, users may improve their proficiency in navigating the digital realm and strengthen their English communication abilities. If utilized judiciously, social media may serve as a valuable instrument for enhancing English language skills and fostering international communication, so contributing to the global improvement of English proficiency levels.

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